

International Trade of Pharmaceutical and Health Industries Along the “Belt and Road” Countries

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Abstract

In recent years, the medical and health industry has become a new engine for global economic development. As a cluster of industries, the level of world's medical and health industry varies. Standards, as a comprehensive reflection and strategic resource of the competitiveness of enterprises, industries, regions, and even countries, have become an important experience and basic consensus for economic development at home and abroad. This article conducts research on the current status of standardization in the pharmaceutical and health industry both domestically and internationally. This study mainly analyzes the bilateral trade volume and industrial structure of pharmaceutical products between China and countries along the “Belt and Road” (BR), and empirically analyzes the influencing factors of pharmaceutical products trade between China and countries along the “Belt and Road” according to the trade situation. Using the explicit comparison index, the trade complementarity index, and the trade intensity index, select fifteen countries that are representative of the trade of pharmaceutical products in China and the regions along “the Belt and Road.” Then, divide pharmaceutical products into traditional Chinese medicine and western medicine. Finally, analyze the problems and challenges that are associated with pharmaceutical products in China and sample countries. Through comparative analysis of organizational structure, standard system, and standard formulation and revision, combined with the practical experience of standardization in BR countries' pharmaceutical and health industry trade, measures and suggestions are proposed on how to accelerate the role of adjustment in pharmaceutical and health industry trade.

More Information

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Introduction

With the development of inland transportation and navigation technology, China's pharmaceutical trade exchanges with countries such as India, Arabia, Japan, North Korea, and Vietnam are becoming increasingly frequent. As a fundamental industry related to national economy and people's livelihood, China's pharmaceutical industry has achieved a relatively fast development speed with the expansion of market size. According to the 2020 Blue Book on the Internationalization of China's Pharmaceutical Industry, China has become the second largest pharmaceutical market in the world after the United States, and the world's largest producer and exporter of active pharmaceutical ingredients [1,2,3].

China

Under policy guidance, China's pharmaceutical and health industry is gradually shifting towards a highly clustered and innovative development model. "Made in China 2025" clearly points out that "we should focus on ten key areas such as biopharmaceuticals and high-performance medical devices" [4,5,6,7]. In addition, the consistency evaluation of generic drugs, reform of the approval system, pilot implementation of the medical device marketing license system, adjustment of the medical insurance drug catalog, and the launch of the "Drug Registration Management Measures" and other heavyweight policies and regulations have created a healthy and sustainable environment for the development of Chinese pharmaceutical production enterprises. The biopharmaceutical industry in China is going through a journey from manufacturing in China to creating in China, from generic drugs to innovative drugs [8].

In terms of spatial distribution, the distribution trend of China's five major pharmaceutical and health industry clusters is prominent [9]. At present, China has initially formed a biopharmaceutical industry cluster with the Yangtze River Delta, Beijing Tianjin Hebei, Chengdu Chongqing Economic Circle, Guangdong Hong Kong Macao Greater Bay Area, and other core areas. In terms of industrial scale, China's pharmaceutical and health industry continues to expand. In 2022, fixed assets investment in pharmaceutical manufacturing increased by 5.9% year on year. In 2022, there were 8814 enterprises above the designated size in the pharmaceutical manufacturing industry nationwide, 477 more than in 2021, with a year-on-year growth of 5.7%. In 2022, enterprises above designated size in the pharmaceutical manufacturing industry achieved a main operating income of 2911.14 billion yuan and a total profit of 428.87 billion yuan. From the perspective of enterprise listing, as of December 2022, there were a total of 1385 biopharmaceutical listed companies in

China, with an annual increase of 111, an increase of 8.71% compared to the previous year [10].

Foreign Countries

The global biopharmaceutical industry is developing in a clustered manner, with developed countries and regions represented by the United States and Japan occupying a dominant position. The Boston Cambridge region of the United States, relying on top educational resources such as Harvard and Boston University, as well as dozens of world-class pharmaceutical companies, has formed a top pharmaceutical center in the United States [11,12]. The industrial clusters in Japan are mainly distributed in Tokyo, Hokkaido, and Kansai. The European biopharmaceutical cluster is mainly distributed in London, Germany's Rhine Delta, and the Bio-valley between Denmark and Sweden.

Belt and Road Countries

Since its proposal, China has signed cooperation agreements with 138 countries and more than 30 international organizations from Europe, North America, Africa, South America, and other countries. The number of cooperation agreements has exceeded 200, and the prosperous cooperation atmosphere has promoted the internationalization process of China's pharmaceutical industry, bringing new development opportunities. In 2016, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and the State Council issued and implemented the "Healthy China 2030" Plan Outline, which further prospered the domestic pharmaceutical and health industry market [13].

The huge market capacity of pharmaceutical products in countries and regions along the BR, together with the upgrading of the Free Trade Agreement, has become a new focus for Chinese pharmaceutical and health enterprises to explore the international market. In recent years, the cooperation between China and the Central and Eastern European ASEAN African countries in the field of "health" has flourished. Mindray Medical has established 21 subsidiaries in 15 countries along the BR. The government level of countries along the line has attached great importance to health cooperation with China, showing a good development prospect. According to IQVIA data, the growth rate of the emerging market pharmaceutical market is expected to reach 5% -8% from 2019 to 2023 [14,15]. It is expected that by 2022, the emerging market pharmaceutical market will account for 56% of the global market. In recent years, China's proportion of pharmaceutical product exports in emerging market countries has been on the rise, and the development potential of pharmaceutical product trade is enormous. The main research content of the paper is divided into the following parts:

- This article mainly conducts empirical research on the factors that affect pharmaceutical trade, and

then calculates the potential for pharmaceutical product trade with sample countries, analyzing the influencing factors.

- Through empirical analysis using a stochastic frontier gravity model, the efficiency, trade potential, and trade potential expansion value of China's pharmaceutical trade with sample countries are studied, Exploring the factors that determine the scale of bilateral pharmaceutical trade from the perspectives of core factors and non-efficiency factors in trade, and
- Finally proposing corresponding policy recommendations based on the analysis of pharmaceutical trade situation and empirical research results.

Methods

This article mainly uses research methods such as literature search, data analysis, and empirical analysis. The specific explanations are as follows:

Literature Search Method

By collecting research literature on trade in pharmaceutical products, "the Belt and Road" trade and trade potential measurement in major databases, we collate the current research status on the above three aspects and find out the deficiencies of current research.

Based on the summary of existing literature, there have been more studies focusing on overseas investment and trade in the pharmaceutical industry, as well as the traditional Chinese medicine or Western medicine industry, with less research on pharmaceutical product trade and multiple qualitative studies. The research on the problems of countries along the "the Belt and Road" is mostly concentrated on the macro level, while the research on the micro level is less. This paper focuses on the trade of Chinese and Western medicines, which is regarded as an innovation.

Data Analysis Method

By searching the official website of the General Administration of Customs of China, the China Chamber of Commerce for Import and Export of Medical and Health Products, UN Contrade, the World Bank and other databases for classification and trade data of China's pharmaceutical product imports and exports, as well as bilateral data on pharmaceutical trade with sample countries, and following the ideas of the article for data processing and analysis.

Under the background of the BR, this paper will use previous studies to measure the trade competitiveness of China's pharmaceutical products by empirical analysis. Introduce relevant factors and use the theory of international trade gravity model to apply a stochastic frontier gravity model to the total trade volume of pharmaceutical products between China and sample countries, in order to calculate the trade efficiency between China and the regions along the

route. The research method can be considered an innovation.

Empirical Analysis Method

By constructing a stochastic frontier gravity model and selecting relevant variables based on the characteristics of the pharmaceutical industry, Frontier 4.1 econometric tool is used to calculate the empirical analysis of pharmaceutical product trade between China and sample countries, calculate trade efficiency, and analyze the influencing factors of trade potential. Previous studies on trade potential have mostly focused on single indicators or incomplete indicator selection. This article divides the factors that affect bilateral pharmaceutical product trade potential into core factors and non-efficiency factors based on the characteristics of the pharmaceutical industry, and creatively introduces cultural distance factors.

Results

According to the requirements for drugs included in the Pharmacopoeia of the People's Republic of China (current version) and the National Essential Medicines, according to the Classification of National Economic Industries, the drugs studied in this article are divided into traditional Chinese medicine and Western medicine. The import and export volume of pharmaceutical products can be queried on the official website of the People's Republic of China Customs according to the main category code in Chapter 30 (Drugs), and the trade volume is expressed in US dollars at current prices.

There are many countries along the "Belt and Road", with different levels of economic development, and large differences in trade scale with countries that have pharmaceutical trade with China. Following the principles of data continuity, availability, and accuracy, the trade of pharmaceutical products between the sample countries and China selected in this paper is large in the countries and regions along the "Belt and Road", and the bilateral trade in medicine is representative. The specific countries and country codes are as follows: Bangladesh (103), India (111), Indonesia (112), Iran (113), Malaysia (122), Pakistan (127), the Philippines (129), Singapore (132), Thailand (136), Türkiye (137), Vietnam (141), Egypt (215), Poland (327), the Russian Federation (344), and Ukraine (347).

Current Situation of China's Foreign Trade in Pharmaceutical Products

According to statistics from China Customs, in 2019, the import and export volume of medical and health products in China reached 145.691 billion US dollars, a year-on-year increase of 26.85%. Among them, exports amounted to 73.83 billion US dollars, a year-on-year increase of 14.6%. Imports increased by 42.5% year-on-year to USD 71.861 billion. The import and export are almost balanced, and the trade surplus has reached a historical low (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Proportion of China's Pharmaceutical Product International Trade Partners

From Figure 1, it can be seen that globally, China's main pharmaceutical trade markets are distributed in North

America, Europe, and Asia. The total trade volume of pharmaceutical products in the top three markets is 132.1 billion US dollars, accounting for 90.5% of the total pharmaceutical trade volume. By country, the United States remains China's largest trading partner in pharmaceutical products, with an import and export volume of 25.857 billion US dollars, a year-on-year increase of 17.89%. The second to fifth ranked countries are Germany, Japan, India, and Ireland. From Figure 2, it can be seen that the export volume of pharmaceutical products in China has been increasing year by year from 2009 to 2023.

Figure 2: Foreign Trade of China's Pharmaceutical Products from 2009 to 2023

In 2009, the export volume of pharmaceutical products in China was only 532000 tons, but by 2023, it had reached 1.109 million tons. The growth rate of pharmaceutical product import trade was relatively small, and it also accounted for a small proportion of the overall trade volume. The trade volume is convenient to look at. Overall, the pharmaceutical trade volume increased year by year from 2009 to 2023, but the growth rate of export trade volume was smaller than that of import trade volume. From a time, span perspective, the export volume of pharmaceutical products was greater than the import volume of pharmaceutical products from 2009 to 2013.

After 2013, the import volume of pharmaceutical products was greater than the export volume and the trade volume showed exponential growth. It can be seen that although the export volume of pharmaceutical products has been increasing year by year, the low added value of products has led to a lower total export value of pharmaceutical products in China. From Figure 3, it can be seen that the size of China's pharmaceutical market was 183.6 billion yuan in 2016, and by 2020, the market size will expand 2.11 times to 387 billion yuan, with an average annual growth rate of 20%.

With technological progress, continuous adjustment of industrial structure, improvement of resident consumption level, and people's own attention to medical and health care, it is expected that by 2025, the

size of China's pharmaceutical market will expand by 215 times compared to 2020, reaching 833.2 billion yuan.

Figure 3: Scale Trends of China's Pharmaceutical Market from 2016 to 2025

Discussion

There are many countries along the "Belt and Road" with different levels of economic development. The trade scale with countries that have pharmaceutical trade in China is quite different. Following the principles of data continuity, availability and accuracy, the trade of pharmaceutical products between the sample countries and China in this paper is large in the countries and regions along the "the Belt and Road". The bilateral trade in pharmaceuticals is representative. The specific country and country codes are as follows: Bangladesh (103), India (111), Indonesia (112), Iran (113), Malaysia (122), Pakistan (127), Philippines (129), Singapore (132), Thailand (136), Türkiye (137), Vietnam (141), Egypt (215), Poland (327), the Russian Federation (344), Ukraine (347), a total of 15 countries.

From 2009 to 2023, the overall display index of traditional Chinese medicine product exports showed a fluctuating upward trend, with indices all greater than 1. Except for 2014, the overall trend showed an increasing trend, representing the continuous strengthening of China's advantages in export trade of

traditional Chinese medicine products. In 2023, the display index of traditional Chinese medicine product exports broke through a historical high of 2.0, with categories such as American ginseng, fresh ginseng, Angelica sinensis, Panax notoginseng, Cordyceps sinensis, licorice, and Codonopsis pilosula having a relatively large trade volume in the export of traditional Chinese medicine products. The export display index of Western medicine products is all below 0.5, with an overall small increase, indicating that the export of Western medicine products does not have an advantage and has a weak competitive advantage in the international market.

From the display comparative advantage index of Chinese traditional medicine products in the sample countries, it can be seen that the RCA of Chinese traditional medicine products are far greater than 1 compared to Russia, Malaysia, Ukraine, Poland, and Indonesia in the three years, indicating that Chinese traditional medicine products have always been in a comparative advantage position in the market competition between the two countries, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Explicit Comparative Advantages of Traditional Chinese Medicine Products in China from 2020 to 2022

The RCA is close to 1 with Thailand, the Philippines, Pakistan, and Egypt, indicating that China's trade advantage in traditional Chinese medicine products with these countries is not obvious. The main reason may be the large production of traditional medicines in Thailand and the Philippines; However, due to their geographical location and cultural differences with our country, Pakistan and Egypt have a relatively small demand for traditional Chinese medicine. Countries with RCA less than 1 mainly include Vietnam, Türkiye, Iran, India and Bangladesh., The competitive advantage of traditional Chinese medicine products in the country's market is relatively weak.

Conclusion

Due to the long time and slow registration process of China's pharmaceutical industry in new drug research and development, the trade barriers imposed by trading countries on China's pharmaceutical product market have resulted in a low-value chain. This can be seen from the import and export trade volume and trade volume of Chinese and Western pharmaceutical products. Although the export volume of traditional Chinese medicine products far exceeds that of Western medicine products, the overall trade volume of traditional Chinese medicine is much lower than that of Western medicine. While the impact of infrastructure on overall trade volume is positive, this positive impact is relatively small and negligible. The convenience of obtaining medical products is also a key factor affecting the interconnection of medical products. From the relationship between trade efficiency, trade potential and trade potential improvement space, China's trade in pharmaceutical products with countries along the BR has excellent overall potential. In terms of specific

countries, the improvement space of trade efficiency and trade potential of pharmaceutical products between Russia and China is polarized. In contrast, the improvement space of trade potential of pharmaceutical products between Singapore, Malaysia, Türkiye, Iran and China is not large. There is a significant difference in the trade potential of pharmaceutical products between the sample countries and China. Specific targeted measures need to be provided to expand the trade volume of pharmaceutical products between the two sides further.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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